

Nutritional Support for Moderate-to-Late-Preterm Infants — A Randomized Trial

ARTICLE SUMMARY

The study investigated nutritional support strategies for moderate-to-late preterm infants who often require support before exclusively feeding on their mother's breast milk, an area with limited evidence-based guidance. In a multicenter, randomized trial, 532 infants born between 32 and 35 weeks' gestation with intravenous access were assigned to three interventions: parenteral nutrition (amino acid solution) or dextrose solution until full milk feeding; milk supplementation versus exclusive maternal breast milk; and taste and smell exposure before gastric-tube feeding or no exposure. The primary outcomes were body-fat percentage at 4 months of corrected gestational age for the nutrition and milk interventions, and time to full enteral feeding for the taste and smell intervention. Results showed no significant differences in body-fat percentage between parenteral nutrition and dextrose (26.0% vs. 26.2%; adjusted mean difference, -0.20; $P = 0.72$) or between milk supplementation and exclusive maternal milk (26.3% vs. 25.8%; adjusted mean difference, 0.65; $P = 0.25$). Similarly, time to full enteral feeding did not differ with taste and smell exposure (5.8 vs. 5.7 days; $P = 0.59$). Secondary outcomes and adverse events were comparable across groups. The study concluded that these routine nutritional interventions had no impact on time to full enteral feeding or body composition at 4 months of corrected age.

AUTHORS

Tanith Alexander: Based at the University of Auckland, Dr. Alexander focuses on neonatal and child health, particularly nutritional interventions and their impact on early development. She has collaborated on research evaluating body composition in children using advanced measurement techniques

Sharin Asadi

Michael Meyer: Dr. Meyer is a member of the DIAMOND Trial Group and works on improving neonatal and preterm infant care. Specific metrics such as h-index were not found in this search; however, his contributions are notable in clinical trials like DIAMOND.

Jane E. Harding: Based at the University of Auckland, Prof. Harding has an h-index of 67 and focuses on maternal and perinatal health, particularly in improving outcomes for preterm infants. Her work spans nutritional strategies and interventions during the neonatal period

Yannan Jiang: Prof. Jiang is a biostatistician at the University of Auckland with expertise in clinical trial design and analysis, contributing to studies in neonatal health and other areas of medicine

Jane M. Alsweiler: Also affiliated with the University of Auckland, Dr. Alsweiler specializes in neonatal endocrinology and the effects of nutrition on preterm infants, including long-term developmental outcomes

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Frank H. Bloomfield: Prof. Bloomfield is a leader in neonatal research, focusing on how nutrition and early-life interventions affect growth and health outcomes. His affiliation with the University of Auckland and involvement in clinical trials like DIAMOND highlight his significant contributions.

JOURNAL

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